

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY****DEVELOPMENT OF LAYOUT FOR PROJECT****Sagar K. Patil*, Prof. Manish D. Mata***Department of Civil Engineering, S.S.G.B. COE, Bhusawal
Department of Civil Engineering, S.S.G.B. COE, Bhusawal

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.155104

ABSTRACT

In the current era Land is one of the premium assets of the holder. This asset is as such that the value of which is appreciating with tremendous increase in comparison with the value of built asset or even gold. The financial transaction in this field has importance if we see the economic growth of any State. Because of this reason State Government has vital role to play in Land Management and making land available for various purpose. The use of land may residential, commercial or industrial other than agriculture. Applying for Tentative layout Approval from Town Planning dept. and relate department. Conducting case study and formulation on actual layout plan for development of agriculture land to non-agriculture land and giving the recommendations regarding the plan from government authorities so that it could be corrected for future.

KEYWORDS: Layout ,Agriculture land , N.A. land , Town planning department, Revenue department, Collector department, Procedure of conversion of land in N.A.land.

INTRODUCTION**Important Terms Use In Project**

Regional Plan- Regional Plan” means a plan for the development or redevelopment of a region which is approved by the State Government and has come into operation under Maharashtra Regional & Town Planning Act, 1966.

Development Plan - Development Plan” means a plan for the development of the area within the jurisdiction of a Planning Authority and includes revision of a development plan and proposals of a Special Planning Authority for development of land within its jurisdictions.

Sub division of land- It is a simple process of dividation of land into small part which are easier to sell.

Layout Open Space / Recreational Open Space-Layout Open Space means a statutory common open space kept in any layout exclusive of margins and approaches, at a height not more than ground level of the building unit.

Amenity Space- For the purpose of these Regulations, amenity space means a statutory space kept in any layout to be used for any of the amenities such as open spaces, parks recreational grounds, playgrounds, sports complex, gardens, convenience shopping, parking lots, primary and secondary schools, clinics, dispensaries, nursery, health club, sub post-office, police station, electric substation, ATM of banks, electronic cyber library, open market, garbage bin, water supply installation, electricity supply installation, sewage treatment plant and includes other utilities, services and conveniences.

Building Line- (For Residential users) The line up to which the plinth of a building adjoining a street or an extension of a street or future street may lawfully extend, It includes the lines prescribed, if any, in any scheme and/ or development plan, or under any other law in force.

Control Line- (For Commercial users) A line on either side of a highway or part of highway beyond the building line fixed in respect of such highway by the Highway Authority.

Owner- The person who has legal title for land or building.(As per 7/12 extract,property cardetc)

Permit / Permission- A permission or authorization in writing by the Authority to carry out the work regulated Development control and promotion Regulations.

Plot / Site- A parcel or piece of land enclosed by definite boundaries and approved by an authority as a building site, under these Regulations.

N.A. Land- Non agriculture land is a land ,on which any activity in the nature of development is carried over on the land which makes land unfit for cultivation.

N.O.C.- Non Objection Certificate.

Important roles play in project

Owner – Approaches Architect/ Engineer for N.A. conversion of land also for tentative layout procedure.

Architect – For preparation of layout plan, architect finds or investigate the zone of the particular lands, it may be residential, agricultural, industrial, commercial, public, semi-public zone. Then, with reference to MPTP Act 1966, & DCPR by laws approved by Maharashtra State and finally prepares the layout plan. Then, Approaches To Concern **Planning Authority**

For **RP Area** – Collector is the planning authority.

For **Municipal Area** – Collector is the planning authority.

For **Nasik, Malegaon** – Commissioner is the Planning Authority.

Revenue department – Sends the application to Town Planning department for Technical Preparation.

Town Planning department- Checking and correcting the plans with consideration of zone , adjoining road, adjoining approved layout, dams, river , any natural activity should not be stopped / interrupted due to N.A. permission.

After all legal and logical checking Town Planning recommends the layout plan for N.A. Approval to Revenue department.

PLANNING FRAME WORK

Actual frame work of the process-

- Client / Owner Comes Towards Architects / Engineer With Following Documents
- 7/12 Extract
- Mojani Nakasha (TILR sheet prepared by TILR department if required)
- Contour Map Of Respective Land
- Other Important Documents.

As per Maharashtra DCPR for RP and Using Rules And Regulations Architect/Engineer Drafts A Layout . After All This Work A Set Of Documents Are Prepared For Submitting In Revenue Department And Town Planning Department.

- Maharashtra Land Revenue Act (1966) Form In Two Set.
- Current 7/12 Extract
- Copies Of The All The Relevant Mutation Entries.
- Extract Of Village Form 8A.
- Certified Copies Of The Land Map From The TalukaInspector ,Taluka Land Record Office.
- Extract Of Cropping Pattern From 1954-55 Till Current Year.
- 5 Blue Print Which Are Sanctioned From Town Planning Department.
- Grampanchayat N.O.C.
- Other N.O.C.'S From Various Government Department.

Finally When All This Process Is Completed Successfully Tentative Layout And Tentative N.A. Order Is Given To The Respective Owner.

After That A New Process Is Further Going On For The Final Approval.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Layout is the process of planning in which a proper development of land is intended a proper sequence of plotting is done with respect to bylaws and rules and regulation. The layout planning is to indicate arrangement of various component or units of a town in such a way that the town is as such attain the significance of living organism.
2. Applying for approval from various departments related to land development, then study and formulation on actual layout plan for development of agriculture land to non-agriculture land and giving the recommendation regarding the failure of plan from government authority, so that it could be correct for future.
3. The open space required is depends on density of population according to standard the open space for outdoor recreational purpose should not be less than 1.0 hect. or 2.5 hect. For 1000 population. Hence the required of open space for a residential neighborhood unit of 10000 population will be: parks for children 1hect, parks and and garden 2 hect. within 1km is used.
4. Depending upon the type of development, bye laws of a locality may be prescribed a definite minimum size of plots for a particular type of development .hence, the minimum sizes of plot for domestic unit is 200sq.m,for semidetached unit 300sq.m and for detached and semidetached building 333sq.m should be provided.
5. The zones are divided into the four categories i.e. residential, commercial, industrial and recreational zone. For zoning purpose the usual percentage of each zone in a normal town varies for residential 40-50 %, commercial zone 2-5%, industrial zone 2-25% and recreational zone remaining percentage.
6. A fundamental aspect that is necessary to emphasize is the necessity of creating awareness about the site layout concept. People generally do not know the problem involved in site layout concept, and tend to work according to their habits, fundamentally based in the traditional conversion way.
7. The implementation of a actual layout plan to be taken having Total area 58800.00sq.m and area under layout 39200.00 sq.m, open space 3701.27sq.m, amenities space 3921.23 sq.m.

CONCLUSION

1. The role of government authority in the layout planning is that they shows us the path that how to prepared a plan with respect to rules and bylaws.
2. The approach for land which is to be developed is find out with the adjoining land which is already developed by considering their approach road it should be connects to the proposed layout plan.
3. For sanctioning the prepared layout for land the role of different department such as town planning department, revenue department, and collector office plays a vital role in developing the layout.
4. The department provides technical assistance to various departments involved in planning and development. this department offers technical remarks to the government in the matters like change of land use proposals, alienation of lands.
5. The Town Planning Board designates and prepares new draft zoning plans, considers proposed layout plans under Comprehensive Development Area zoning, exhibits draft plans for public comment, considers applications for planning permission, and submits draft plans for approval by the Chief Executive in Council.
6. The goal of a new integrated approach to planning the use and management of land resources is to make optimal and informed choices on the future uses of the land.
7. By adopting the rules and regulation govern by Municipal Corporation we can prepares a proper planning as per bylaws.
8. By adopting certain proper planning technique we can develop a proper suitable and systematically develop plan.
9. Formulation of actual layout plan for development of agriculture land to nonagricultural land and giving the recommendations regarding the failure of plan from government authorities so that it could be corrected for future.
10. The land which is to be intended to be used as a layout purpose should be zoned on residential zoning.
11. Planning framework for sanctioning of layout for proposed area right from planning stage to completion stage is controlled by various authority the mainly of them are town planning department.
12. For developing any layout zoning is very essential factor.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This achievement would be worthless if it was not for the timely help and guidance of well-wishers. I know an acknowledgement is not enough to scale their help and wishes, yet I take this opportunity to express my gratitude

to every element without which the project work would not have shaped. I would like to express my profound gratitude and great appreciation to my guide **Prof. Manish Mata** and **H.O.D. Prof. P.P. Bhangale** for their encouragement, valuable advice, constructive suggestions, tireless guidance and enduring patience throughout this study. I am thankful to Consulting Engineer **Mr. J. A. Nagmoti**, Assistant Town Planner **Mr. Imran Khan Pathan**, Nashik branch, Town Planner **Mr. Vilas Patil**, Nashik branch, Nayab Tahasildar **Mr. B. Aawari**, Nashik, Assistant Town Planner **Mrs. Sarode, Mrs Kajale**, Thane branch. Those provided me all information regarding project layout planning and helped me throughout my work. I would like to thank **Prof. Dr. R. P. Singh**, Principal of the institute who has provided me this opportunity to present this Project and also thankful to our Central library, Departmental library and all other staff members of Civil engineering Department for their help and co-operation. Last but not the least I acknowledge deep indebtedness to my parents and friends for their inspiration and all known and unknown helping hands for their help and co- operation in all phases of the project.

REFERENCES

- [1] Schlebusch, Sanmarie&CilliersElizelle, Juanee,(2013),*Planning For Sustainable Communities: Layout And Design Approaches*,Planning For Sustainable Communities 49th ISOCARP Congress,2013.
- [2] YahyuKadioglu, *Land Use And Major Issues Of Planning In City Of Trabzon*,Science Direct Procedia Social And Behavioral Sciences 19, (2011),PP-354-362.
- [3] S SYasmin Sofia Hussain, Ismail Said(2015), *Knowledge Integration Between Planning And Landscape Architecture In Contributing To A Better Open Space*, Science Direct Procedia- Social And Behavioral Sciences 170, (2015),PP-545-556.
- [4] Arnis Cirulis,*3D Outdoor Augmented Reality For Architecture And Urban Planning*, Science Direct Procedia Computer Science 25 ,(2013),PP-71-79.
- [5] HariPrasad.Na, Rajyalakshmi.Gb, SreenivasuluReddy.Ac(2014),*A Typical Manufacturing Plant Layout Design Using CRAFT Algorithm*,Science Direct Procedia Engineering 97, (2014),PP-1808-1814.
- [6] *Simplification Of Legal And Procedural Framework For Conversion Of Agricultural Land To Non-Agricultural Purposes*,Optional Reform Under JNNURM.
- [7] Association of New Jersey Environmental Commissions Smart Growth Survival Kit," *The Master Plan: Smart Growth, the Master Plan & Environmental Protection*".
- [8] *The Maharashtra Land Revenue* (Conversion Of Use Of Land And Non-Agriculture Assessment) *Rules*, 1966.
- [9] Das, A.K., "*Urban Planning in India*",Rawat Publisher, 2007.
- [10]Chand M., Puri, V. K., "*Regional Planing in India*", Allied Publishers Limited, 2011.
- [11]Rangwala, "*Town Planning*",Charotar Publication, 27th Edition, 2014.PP-27-52.
- [12]*Standardized Development Control and Promotion Regulations For Regional Plans In Maharashtra*. SANCTIONEDVIDE GOVERNMENT NOTIFICATION NO-TPS-1812/15/CR71/12/REC NO 34/12/UD 13/ DT. 21st November 2013.